

11TH EDITION

*THE INTERNATIONAL
SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE*

LITERATURE, DISCOURSE AND MULTICULTURAL DIALOGUE

TÎRGU MUREȘ

9-10 DECEMBER 2023

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CONFERENCE SCHEDULE

SATURDAY- 9 DECEMBER 2023

- **Literature**
- **Language and Discourse**
- **Communication, Journalism, Education Sciences, Psychology and Sociology**
- **History, Political Sciences, International Relations**
- **Social Sciences**

The conference is organised in partnership by:

*"Alpha" Institute for Multicultural Studies
"Gh. Șincai" Institute for Social Sciences and the Humanities
"Dimitrie Cantemir" University of Tîrgu Mureș*

A WORD FROM THE PRESIDENT OF THE CONFERENCE

Dear Guests,

Having established a certain tradition in the recent years, the International Conference *LITERATURE, DISCOURSE AND MULTICULTURAL DIALOGUE* (now at its 11th edition) intends to unite emerging scholars, as well as prestigious researchers from different fields of radical relevance for the contemporary society, a society that is supposed to secure its future not only on the economic and ecological level, but also on the spiritual one. Literature, the cultural discourses as well as the arts gain new connections and dimensions through fundamental changes and structural progress, so that the social end-results of education and research becomes extremely important. It is a fact that in our postmodern times, we live in a society of knowledge, from which we benefit directly in our everyday life, but to the risks and dangers of which we are at the same time exposed. *Non scholae sed vitae discimus* (*We do not learn for the school, but for life*) becomes a creed that every academic institution has to put into practice by means of its activities. It is essential that the path between education and research is very short, especially in academic systems. Research generates new knowledge, creates a favourable atmosphere for change, and provides people with information and data which help them to become aware of the mysteries of the universe and to make the most of their activity in all fields of knowledge. In this interesting and captivating century, to the noble mission of educating the younger generations we must also add the fruit of the efforts in research, materialized in interesting works and papers, together with ideas

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generated by the creative ability which ennobles the personality of the academic.

I wish to express my hope that this scientific event will take place under the most favourable auspices and that it will represent a remarkable starting point for further evolution and development in the field of knowledge. Let this international conference provide a good opportunity for us to gain and transfer knowledge, to generate new theories in the world of science – essential aspirations of any contemporary research.

Prof. IULIAN BOLDEA, PhD
President of the *LDMD 11* Conference

SATURDAY – 9 DECEMBER 2023

LITERATURE

Moderators: Prof. Iulian Boldea, PhD, UMFST Tîrgu Mureş; Assoc. Prof. Luiza Catrinel Marinescu, PhD, Romanian Language Institute, University of “St Kliment Ohridsky” Sofia, Bulgaria; Assoc. Prof. Dumitru-Mircea Buda, PhD, UMFST Tîrgu Mureş.

1. Iulian Boldea, Prof., PhD, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureş, *NORMAN MANEA. THE ETHICS OF MEMORY AND THE DILEMMAS OF IDENTITY*
2. Maria-Mina Rusu, Prof., PhD, „Apollonia” University of Iaşi, *THE DIARY - THE ROAD OF HISTORY TO LITERATURE*
3. Lavinia-Magdalena Bănică, Assoc. Prof., PhD, National University of Science and Technology „Politehnica” Bucharest, University Center of Piteşti, *PICTO-LITERATURE-AN INNOVATIVE FORM IN ROMANIAN TEXTS FROM THE 17TH-18TH CENTURIES*
4. Luiza Catrinel Marinescu, Assoc. Prof., PhD, Romanian Language Institute, University „St. Kliment Ohridsky”, Sofia, *THE ALGORITHMIZATION BY WORD: EUGEN LOVINESCU (1881-1943) - MONICA LOVINESCU (1923-2008)*
5. Nicoleta Crînganu, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Dunărea de Jos” University of Galaţi, *CHILDREN’S LITERATURE – BETWEEN THE LITERARY AND THE DIDACTIC*
6. Emanuela Ilie, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iaşi, Luiza Negură, PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iaşi, *A PROVOCATIVE MANIFESTO FOR THE COUNTRY BEYOND POETRY. DIMENSIONS AND EXPRESSIONS OF RESISTANCE IN ILEANA MĂLĂNCIOIU’S POLITICAL POETRY*

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7. Nicoleta Sălcudeanu, Scientific Researcher, PhD, „Gheorghe Șincai” Institute for Social Sciences, Târgu Mureș, Romanian Academy, *THE DIARY AS ENCODED CONFSSIONAL*
8. Amada Mocioalcă, Lecturer, PhD, University of Craiova, *MARLOWE AND RENAISSANCE MAGIC*
9. Iulian Băicuș, Lecturer, PhD, University of Bucharest, *WHEN CLIO WANTS TO BECOME MELPOMENE*
10. Irina-Ana Drobot, Lecturer, PhD, Technical University of Civil Engineering Bucharest, *THE IMAGE OF AUTUMN IN THE POEM OCTOBER BY ION MINULESCU*
11. Maria Lațchici, Lecturer, PhD, University of Bucharest, *FEMININE DESTINIES IN THE PROSE OF JOSIP KOZARAC*
12. Alexandra Burghilea-Arabu, Lecturer, PhD, Politehnica University of Bucharest, *CULTURAL BORROWINGS IN LA CORONACIÓN BY JUAN DE MENA*
13. Iudit Călinescu, Lecturer, PhD, Romanian Language Institute, Bucharest, University of Szeged, Hungary, *ROMANIAN POETS FROM HUNGARY*
14. Mihai Ion, Lecturer, PhD, „Transilvania” University of Brașov, *POLYMORPHISM OF HUMAN CONDITION IN SUDDENLY, A KNOCK ON THE DOOR BY ETGAR KERET*
15. Violeta-Teodora Lungeanu, Lecturer, PhD, „Dunărea de Jos” University of Galați, *MIRCEA ELIADE’S INDIA – SEARCHING FOR A PATTERN OF EXISTENCE AT THE INTERSECTION OF SELF AND THE OTHER*
16. Calina Paliciuc, Lecturer, PhD, „Aurel Vlaicu” University of Arad, *THE CHRISTIAN RELIGIOUS ELEMENT IN GOGA’S LYRICS*
17. Miruna Ciocoi-Pop, Assist. Prof., PhD, „Lucian Blaga” University of Sibiu, *DEATH - A DEFINING ELEMENT IN THE CONSTRUCTION OF YASUNARI KAWABATA’S SNOW COUNTRY*
18. Maximiliana Ștefan (Mihet), PhD, „1 Decembrie 1918” University of Alba Iulia, *THE MANIFESTATION OF THE*

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SACRED THROUGH THE SYMBOL IN THE ELIADESCIAN WRITING „THE SNAKE”

19. Dorina-Mădălina Lazăr, PhD, University of Bucharest, *MICHEL FOUCAULT AND THE „HETEROTOPIC SPACE”*
20. Laura-Teodora Voinescu, PhD, *FERNANDA MELCHOR, THE POWER OF WRITING*
21. Daniel Kițu, PhD, „Gheorghe Munteanu Murgoci” National College, Brăila, *THE DELTAIC IMAGINARY – ABOUT A MYTHOLOGY OF THE DICHOTOMOUS TOPOI*
22. Elena Atudosiei, PhD, Secondary School „Elena Cuza” and Secondary School „Bogdan Petriceicu Hașdeu” Iași, *THE LAST IMMORTAL EMPEROR – JOURNEY TO A NEW ADVENTURE*
23. Alexandra Ruscanu, PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *THE IMAGINARY OF FEMININITY IN DIFFERENT FORMS OF SCIENCE FICTION DISCOURSE*
24. Cornelia Alina Musat, PhD Student, University of Craiova, *THE DIALECTICS OF SELF CONFIGURATIONS IN ALAIN ROBBE-GRILLET'S LES ROMANESQUES TRILOGY*
25. Ana-Maria Florea (Floroiu), PhD Student, National University of Science and Technology „Politehnica” Bucharest, University Center of Pitești, *THE RECEPTION OF PANAIT CERNA'S WORKS*
26. Camelia-Vasilica Munteanu (Gheorghisor), PhD Student, National University of Science and Technology „Politehnica” Bucharest, *UNDER THE SIGN OF CLIO*
27. Carmen Gabriela Popa, PhD Student, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, *FRANCO MORETTI – ON THE LITERARY SURVIVAL*
28. Elena Tudose, PhD Student, University of Craiova, *INTROSPECTION - COURAGE OR MADNESS?*
29. Gilda – Daniela Iani (Chirilută), PhD Student, „Dunărea de Jos” University of Galați, *MIMESIS OF REMEMBERING IN “HOW TO FORGET A WOMAN”*

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30. Gloria-Laura Jercău (Ghidiceanu), PhD Student, University of Craiova, *GELLU NAUM AND THE TRAVELER APOLLODORUS*
31. Laurențiu Boșog, PhD Student, University of Craiova, *ITALY, TRAVEL LITERATURE AND AESTHETIC EXPECTATIONS*
32. Luminița-Erika Velker (Colopelnic), PhD Student, Technical University of Cluj-Napoca, *FEMININE TYPOLOGIES IN TEODOR MAZILU'S SHORT PROSE*
33. Marinela-Alexandra Enache-Popa, PhD Student, University of Craiova, *UNIVERSAL PERSPECTIVES OF THE VISIONARY E.M. CIORAN - OXYMORONIC AND CONTRADICTORY EMOTIONS*
34. Mirela-Cristina Coman (Liuță), PhD Student, „Ștefan cel Mare” University of Suceava, *LOVE'S RESORTS IN "JACOB SE HOTĂRĂȘTE SĂ IUBEASCĂ" NOVEL BY CĂTĂLIN DORIAN FLORESCU*
35. George Panțică, PhD Student, „Dunărea de Jos” University of Galați, *THE DEBUT OF ADRIAN PĂUNESCU BETWEEN ETHICS AND AESTHETICS*
36. Paul-Cristian Albu, PhD Student, University of Craiova, *SAMUEL BECKETT- GENIUS OR A MAD? A PANORAMIC VIEW OF THE REFLECTION OF HIS GENIUS IN CONTEMPORARY LITERATURE*
37. Rodica Ileana Stan (Olteanu Moldovan), PhD Student, „1 Decembrie 1918” University of Alba Iulia, *COUPLE'S IMAGE FROM BIOGRAPHY TO LITERARY PROJECTION: ANA BLANDIANA - ROMULUS RUSAN*
38. Sergiu Crăciun, PhD Student, „Ștefan cel Mare” University of Suceava, *POPULAR FAIRY TALES COLLECTED BY MIHAI LUPESCU: SOME LEVELS OF INTERPRETATION*
39. Simona-Sanda Avram, PhD Student, National University of Science and Technology „Politehnica” Bucharest, *TRAIAN DORZ, THE REFLECTION OF LIFE IN POETRY*

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40. Rebeca-Daniela Stănescu, PhD Student, National University of Science and Technology „Politehnica” Bucharest, University Center of Pitești, *URMUZ AND THE LITERATURE APOCALYPSE*
41. Ionela Florina Bolbea (Ene), PhD Student, National University of Science and Technology „Politehnica” Bucharest, *CHRONOLOGICAL STYLISTIC ADEQUACY IN TRANSLATIONS*
42. Elena Breja, PhD Student, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, *THE BUCOLIC IN ION PILLAT'S LYRICISM*
43. Elena Breja, PhD Student, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, *NATURE MYTHOLOGICAL AND FOLKLORE ELEMENTS IN THE WORK OF ION PILLAT*
44. Carmen-Daniela Berințan, PhD Student, Technical University of Cluj-Napoca, North University Center of Baia Mare, *ABOUT THE BEAUTY OF MELANCHOLY IN MIRCEA CĂRTĂRESCU'S „MELANCHOLY”*
45. Smărândița-Elena Costin, PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *THE OTHER HASDEU? THE POSTURAL DIAGNOSIS OF A „CORRESPONDENCE FOR ETERNITY”*

LANGUAGE AND DISCOURSE

Moderators: Prof. Diana Dănișor, PhD, University of Craiova; Prof. Floriana Popescu, PhD, „Dunărea de Jos” University of Galați; Assoc. Prof. Ioana-Crina Prodan, PhD, „Ștefan cel Mare” University of Suceava

1. Diana Dănișor, Prof., PhD, University of Craiova, Georgeta-Amelia Motoi, Lecturer, PhD, University of Craiova, *THE POWER OF WORDS - PERFORMATIVE VERBS IN LEGAL COMMUNICATION*
2. Floriana Popescu, Prof., PhD, „Dunărea de Jos” University of Galați, Cristina Mihaela Popescu, Assist. Prof., PhD, „Dunărea de Jos” University of Galați, *EPONYMISMS ARE A PRECIOUS LEGACY*
3. Roxana Anca Trofin, Assoc. Prof., PhD, *National University of Science and Technology “Politehnica” Bucharest, LA POLITIQUE LINGUISTIQUE ET LE PLURILINGUISME À L’UNIVERSITÉ - QUELLES RETOMBÉES SUR L’ENSEIGNEMENT DU FRANÇAIS?*
4. Ioana-Crina Prodan, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Ștefan cel Mare” University of Suceava, *POUR UNE APPROCHE DES CHAMPS TRADITIONNELS DE LA LINGUISTIQUE*
5. Alina Roșcan, Assoc. Prof., PhD, “Carol I” National Defence University, Bucharest, *APPEALS TO EMOTIONS IN THE RECRUITING CAMPAIGNS OF THE ROMANIAN MINISTRY OF DEFENSE*
6. Dana Carmen Zechia, Lecturer, PhD, „Mircea cel Bătrân” Naval Academy of Constanța, *ESP TEACHING AND LEARNING IN THE MODERN DIGITAL WORLD*
7. Dănuța Magdalena Pruneanu, Lecturer, PhD, National University of Science and Technology „Politehnica”

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- Bucharest, University Center of Pitești, *LEXICAL STRUCTURES IN THE POETRY FROM „GÂNDIREA” MAGAZINE*
8. Dănuța Magdalena Pruneanu, Lecturer, PhD, National University of Science and Technology „Politehnica” Bucharest, University Center of Pitești, *CURRENT TRENDS MANIFESTED IN THE ROMANIAN LEXICON*
 9. Adriana Elena Geantă, Senior Lecturer, PhD, University of Pitești, *RULES FOR WRITING ACCURATELY WITH I, II, III*
 10. Marta-Teodora Boboc, Lecturer, PhD, University of Bucharest, *RETERMINOLOGISATION AS A MEANS OF LEXICAL ENRICHMENT AT LSP LEVEL*
 11. Liliana Tronea-Ghidel, Assist. Prof., PhD, University of Craiova, *ANIMAL PROVERBS IN ENGLISH AND THEIR ROMANIAN EQUIVALENTS*
 12. Liliana Tronea-Ghidel, Assist. Prof., PhD, University of Craiova, *ENGLISH PROVERBS ON FRIENDS AND FAMILY*
 13. Garofița Dincă, Scientific Researcher, PhD, „Iorgu Iordan – Alexandru Rosetti” Institute of Linguistics of the Romanian Academy, Bucharest, *A PARODY OF THE NOVEL IN BOUVARD ET PÉCUCHEZ BY GUSTAVE FLAUBERT OR THE CLAIMED-INVOLUNTARY TRANSFORMATION OF THE LANGUAGE’S REFERENTIAL FUNCTION TO AN EXPRESSIVE FUNCTION*
 14. Mădălina Toader, Assist. Prof., PhD, University of Bucharest, *CULTURAL AND LINGUISTIC ADAPTATION IN WRITING CVs AND COVER LETTERS FOR BUSINESS FRENCH STUDENTS*
 15. Violeta Berbaru Oneata, PhD, „I.L. Caragiale” National College, Ploiești, *INTERFERENCES (II)*
 16. Diana Bunaciu, PhD Student, „Aurel Vlaicu” University of Arad, *SATIRE EXPRESSIONS AS A LITERARY GENRE IN BRAVO MAGAZINE*

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17. Valentina Andreea Popovici, PhD Student, Free International University of Moldova, Republic of Moldova, *ECHINOX – THE SEARCH OF A NEW ROLE*
18. Emanuela Păduraru, PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *PERSPECTIVES ON MODAL VERBS IN CURRENT ROMANIAN AND GERMAN JOURNALISTIC DISCOURSE*
19. Emilia-Mihaela Costescu (Crînguș), PhD Student, University of Craiova, *THE SUFFIX –AN IN JOURNALISTIC LANGUAGE*
20. Emilia-Mihaela Costescu (Crînguș), PhD Student, University of Craiova, *JOURNALISTIC LANGUAGE. THE SUFFIX - ISM*
21. Gabriela Stanciu-Șerban, PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *TEACHING LANGUAGES*
22. Isabelle Nicole Voicu, PhD Student, „Lucian Blaga” University of Sibiu, *AN OVERVIEW OF REFORMULATION*
23. Loredana-Georgiana Popescu (Tomescu), PhD Student, University of Craiova, *THE LEXICAL-GRAMMATICAL HOMONYMS MÂNĂ, MINTE, OCHI IN THE DICTIONARIES OF THE ROMANIAN LANGUAGE*
24. Oana Balan, PhD Student, State University of Moldova, Chișinău, Republic of Moldova, *LINGUISTIC RELATIVITY IN ANTONYMIC ENGLISH AND ROMANIAN PHRASEOLOGIES FOR SUCCESS AND UNSUCCESS*
25. Oana Șulic, PhD Student, State University of Moldova, Chișinău, Republic of Moldova, *THE CONCEPT OF DREAM AS HOPE IN THE ROMANIAN, FRENCH AND ENGLISH LINGUISTIC IMAGINARY*
26. Iuliana Nedelcu (Neacșu), PhD Student, “Ovidius” University of Constanța, *THE INFLUENCE OF THE FRENCH LANGUAGE ON ROMANIAN PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS*

***COMMUNICATION, JOURNALISM, EDUCATION
SCIENCES, PSYCHOLOGY AND SOCIOLOGY***

Moderators: Prof. Teodor Pătrăuță, PhD, "Vasile Goldiș" West University of Arad; Prof. Axinia Crasovschi, University of Bucharest; Assoc. Prof. Laura Ioana Leon, „Grigore T. Popa” University of Medicine and Pharmacy, Iași

1. Teodor Pătrăuță, „Vasile Goldiș” West University of Arad, *INTERCULTURAL OPENNESS – REALITY AND REQUIREMENT OF CONTEMPORARY EDUCATION*
2. Tatiana Callo, Prof., PhD, „Ion Creangă” State Pedagogical University of Chișinău, Moldova, *MODERN EPISTEMOLOGY OF ELITE PEDAGOGY*
3. Axinia Crasovschi, Prof., PhD, University of Bucharest, *COMBINING THE RUSSIAN DINNER AND THE FRENCH LUNCH IN THE ROMA SALAD OR THE DUALISM OF CULTURES (THE ESSAY OF MARINA TSVETAeva)*
4. Adrian Ghicov, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Ion Creangă” State Pedagogical University of Chișinău, Moldova, *COMPETENCE AND NEURO-LEARNING IN THE SPACE OF UNIVERSITY PEDAGOGY*
5. Claudia Florina Pop, Assoc. Prof., PhD, University of Oradea, *THE ROLE OF MENTORING AND COACHING ACTIVITIES IN VOLUNTEERING PROJECTS*
6. Laura Ioana Leon, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Grigore T. Popa” University of Medicine and Pharmacy, Iași, *VISUAL AND NARRATIVE DISTORTIONS OF REALITY IN TAFFY BRODESSER ACKNER'S FLEISHMAN IS IN TROUBLE*
7. Mihaela Mureșan, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Babeș-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca, *THE PROCESS OF*

ROMANISATION OF RECENTLY ENTERED ANGLICISMS INTO THE JOURNALISTIC LANGUAGE

8. Cojocari-Luchian Snejana, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Ion Creangă” State Pedagogical University of Chişinău, Moldova, *ETHNIC-SOCIAL-SCHOOL ENVIRONMENT AS EDUCATIONAL FACTORS IN PROMOTING INTERCULTURALITY*
9. Marius-Valeriu Grecu, Assoc. Prof., PhD, University of Piteşti, *THE CONTRIBUTION OF THE DIDACTIC GAME IN THE TEACHING-LEARNING ACTIVITY OF THE NOTIONS OF ROMANIAN LANGUAGE IN PRIMARY CLASSES*
10. Veronica Gaspar, Assoc. Prof., PhD, National University of Music, Bucharest, *THE HIDDEN TEACHER*
11. Călin-Daniel Paţulea, Lecturer, PhD, „Babeş – Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca, *THE INTEGRATIVE PSYCHOPEDAGOGY OF JESUS - METHOD OF DEVELOPING THE INTEGRALITY, SANCTITY AND FULLNESS OF LIFE OF THE HUMAN PERSON*
12. Lia-Maria Cioanca, Lecturer, PhD, „Babeş-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca, *THE IMPACT OF RURAL TOURISM DEVELOPMENT ON THE LOCAL COMMUNITY. CASE STUDY: SÂNCRAIU VILLAGE, CLUJ COUNTY, ROMANIA*
13. Alexandru Condache, Lecturer, PhD, West University of Timişoara, *TIKTOK „SERVING” CULTURE. CASE STUDY: TIMIŞOARA 2023*
14. Anuţa Ionescu, Lecturer, PhD, National University of Science and Technology „Politehnica” Bucharest, University Center of Piteşti, *THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE PRE-SCHOOLERS VOCABULARY THROUGH THE DIDACTIC GAME*
15. Andreea Ignat, Lecturer, PhD, „Dimitrie Cantemir” University of Târgu Mureş, *EFFICIENT ACCOUNTING-RELATED COMMUNICATION*
16. Oana-Andreea Nae, Lecturer, PhD, „Dunărea de Jos” University of Galaţi, *THE JOURNALISTIC LANGUAGE IN REPORTING THE ARMED CONFLICT BETWEEN ISRAEL AND*

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THE GAZA STRIP. HOW BOUNDARIES, AGGRESSION AND FEAR ARE PERCEIVED

17. Cezar Sigmirean, Assist. Prof., PhD, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, *MULTICULTURALISM AND SOCIAL INCLUSION THROUGH ADVERTISING CAMPAIGNS*
18. Oana Enache, Assist. Prof., PhD, „Dunărea de Jos” University of Galați, *INTEGRATED DESIGN OF ACTIVITIES ON EXPERIENTIAL DOMAINS IN KINDERGARTEN, FROM THEMATIC INTEGRATION TO CONTENT INTEGRATION*
19. Iulia Adelina Ghiță, Assist. Prof., PhD, „Petroleum-Gas” University of Ploiești, *EXPLORING THE IMPACT OF STUDY ROOM ENVIRONMENT ON STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE*
20. Samira Cîrlig, Scientific Researcher, European Center for Ethnic Studies, Romanian Academy, PhD Student, University of Bucharest, *THE INVESTMENTS OF THE HUNGARIAN STATE VS. THE INVESTMENTS OF THE HUNGARIAN STATE IN THE HARGHITA COVASNA AREA – A CROSSING FROM „MITTELPUNKT” TO „HINTERLAND” THROUGH A SYMBOLIC MOVEMENT OF THE BORDER?*
21. Ovidiu Ionel Duta, Research Assistant, „Babeș-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca, *V.A.X REALITY – THE CURRENT STATE OF AFFAIRS*
22. Iulia Alecu Buza, PhD, „Titu Maiorescu” University, *MULTICULTURALISM IN HIGHER EDUCATION ARIA*
23. Olga Balanici, PhD Student, „Ion Creangă” State Pedagogical University of Chișinău, Moldova, *PEDAGOGICAL PERSPECTIVES ON EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT APPROACH*
24. Crina-Ancuța Macovei, PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *SILENT PERSUASION: DISCOVERING THE POWER OF NONVERBAL PERSUASIVE STRATEGIES IN ADVERTISING*

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25. Teodor-Sorin Cumpănășoiu, PhD Student, Free International University of Moldova, Chișinău, Republic of Moldova, *THE IMPACT OF THE FAMILY ENVIRONMENT ON TEENAGERS' SCHOOL RESULTS*
26. Mona-Elena Cozma, PhD Student, „Ion Creangă” State Pedagogical University, Chișinău, Republic of Moldova, *INCREASING PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS' MOTIVATION FOR READING THROUGH ICT*
27. Mihaela Sandu, PhD Student, „Ion Creangă” State Pedagogical University of Chișinău, Moldova, *THE VALORISATION OF SOME ASPECTS OF PSYCHO-PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT IN CHILDREN IN RELATION WITH THEIR PARENTS' INVOLVEMENT*
28. Ana Hîrțan, PhD Student, „Ion Creangă” State Pedagogical University of Chișinău, Republic of Moldova, *EDUCATION THROUGH VALUES IN THE CONTEXT OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION*
29. Smărândița-Elena Costin, PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *EPISTOLARY INSERTS IN CHILDREN'S LITERATURE. SUGGESTIONS OF (EXTRA)CURRICULAR PRACTICES FOR THE THREE CYCLES OF PRE-UNIVERSITY STUDY*
30. Ionela Maria Brașoveanu (Ion), University of Craiova, *THE “STREET PEOPLE” PHENOMENON - RISKS AND CONSEQUENCES OF STREET LIFE*

SATURDAY – 9 DECEMBER 2023

**HISTORY, POLITICAL SCIENCES, INTERNATIONAL
RELATIONS**

*Moderators: Prof. Cornel Sigmirean, PhD, UMFST Tîrgu Mureş;
Prof. Mădălina Strehie, PhD, University of Craiova; Assoc. Prof.
Ioana-Iulia Olaru, PhD, „G. Enescu” National University of Arts, Iaşi*

1. Cornel Sigmirean, Prof., PhD, UMFST „G.E. Palade” of Târgu Mureş, *THE ETHOS OF EDUCATION AND THE IDEA OF A ROMANIAN UNIVERSITY IN TRANSYLVANIA IN THE 19TH CENTURY*
2. Ioana-Iulia Olaru, Prof., PhD, „G. Enescu” National University of Arts, Iaşi, *PAINTING AND ENGRAVING IN AFRICAN NEOLITHIC*
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